

18PRT01 PROBE TRACE TRACEABILITY FOR CONTACT PROBE AND STYLUS INSTRUMENT MEASUREMENTS

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Abstract - The Probe Trace Project - Traceability for contact probe and stylus instrument measurements funded under the European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) has been presented in this article. The overall goal of this project is to develop traceable and cost-effective measurement capabilities for the calibration of form and surface roughness standards with uncertainties in the range 10 nm – 100 nm. To achieve targeted uncertainties noise reduction software with numerical methods for random noise bias reduction, will be developed to be used to pre-process roughness and form profile data. The project will provide new routes and novel methods for achieving direct traceability to the SI unit, the metre instead of the current necessity of using artefacts with fixed nominal values utilising accessible and portable displacement generators.

I. INTRODUCTION

The surface texture and form of the product are important features of the production process that are measured for engineering and scientific purposes. Such characteristics of surfaces include wear resistance, bearing, sliding and lubricating properties, fatigue and corrosion resistance, functionality etc. In the manufacturing industry, surface properties are checked to be within certain limits of roughness and form. Therefore, accurate measurement of surface roughness and shape is critical to quality control of processing.

In real production conditions, form errors are mainly measured by coordinate measuring devices (CMMs) which are key measuring devices for the factory of the future (Industry 4.0). Demands for the fastest possible measurements have led to a new generation of CMMs operating in scan mode and measuring both dimensions and shape at the same time. When the contact measurement probes are used in continuous (scanning) mode with CMMs, the dynamic performance of the probes must be evaluated. [1]

Up to now, there is no guidance document for calibration of measurement probes. The guides for calibration of stylus instruments (DKD-R 4.2 and ISO 5436) [2, 3] provides information using only conventional reference standards such as depth setting and surface roughness standards traceable to reference interference microscopes and reference complex stylus devices available in a few advanced NMIs.

Therefore, in 2019, the EMPIR project entitled Traceability for contact probe and stylus instrument measurements was launched. The project consortium brings together the leading European NMIs and DIs in traceability for contact probes and stylus instrument measurements. It is complemented by two non-European NMIs that bring in their specific knowledge and experience. [1]

The main goal of this project is to develop traceable and cost-effective measurement capabilities for calibrating of form and surface roughness standards with uncertainties in the range 10 nm – 100 nm. The basic idea of the project is to replace the numerous physical standards used to calibrate the stylus instruments as well as reference

probes for form measurements using novel portable displacement generators. To achieve targeted uncertainties noise reduction software will be developed, including the use of numerical methods for random noise bias reduction, that can be used to pre-process roughness and form profiles data to reduce the overall uncertainties down to a level of 10 nm in roughness and roundness measurements. [1]

II. CALIBRATION OF CONTACT STYLUS INSTRUMENTS USING DISPLACEMENT GENERATORS

Stylus instruments use a probe to detect the surface, physically moving a probe along the surface to acquire the surface height data (Figure 1). The instrument records vertical changes in the position of the probe tip, which correspond to irregularities on the surface, and converts them into an electrical signal with a converter, which is further processed in the computer unit of the measuring instrument.

The characteristics of material measures used as measurement standards for the calibration of metrological characteristics of stylus instruments are defined in standard ISO 5436-1:2000 Geometrical Product Specifications (GPS) – Surface texture: Profile method; Measurement standards – Part 1: Material measures. The calibration of the existing wide range of stylus instruments calls for more than one type of measurement standard. Table 1 provides an overview of the standards according to the ISO 5436-1:2000.

TABLE I
TYPES OF MEASUREMENT STANDARDS [3]

Type	Name	Profile
A	Depth measurement standard	
B	Tip condition measurement standard	
C	Spacing measurement standard	
D	Roughness measurement standard	
E	Profile coordinate measurement standard	

Each measurement standard has a limited range of application according to its own characteristics and those of the instrument to be calibrated with only specific nominal values. For example, depth standards are produced in certain depth values (e.g. 2 μm , 5 μm , 10 μm , 900 μm). Using those standards, the stylus instruments are

calibrated only at this specific depth value (at discrete steps). The values between them (e.g. 10-900 μm) are interpolated by the stylus instrument, assuming it is working properly. [1]

Due to the above-elaborated Probe Trace project will provide new routes and novel methods for achieving direct traceability to the SI unit, the metre using displacement generators instead of the current necessity of using artefacts with fixed nominal values. Also, calibrations carried out using displacement generators will make continuous sampling possible, whereas when depth setting standards are used, only discrete sampling is possible.

Displacement transducers can measure/generate very small displacement steps (down to 1 nm) utilising various reference measurement systems such as laser interferometers, capacitive sensors, linear encoders etc. They are equipped with motorised systems (mostly piezoelectric systems for high precision applications) to generate precise displacement steps at nm levels. They can be calibrated by applying laser displacement interferometers to provide direct traceability to the SI unit, the metre, Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Displacement transducer calibration scheme.

III. CALIBRATION OF FORM MEASUREMENT PROBES USING DISPLACEMENT GENERATORS

Form measurement probes are crucial part of form measuring devices and they are used for converting small displacements into electrical signal which is further processed in the computer unit of the measuring device.

Most of form measuring system have possibilities of changing angle, probe diameter or length of probe tip. Every change in system will lead to error in measuring signal, mostly because of the change in systems gain. Therefore, gain should be corrected on regular basis, typically by measuring known displacement provided by measurement standards i.e calibration on regular basis is needed.

Form measurement probes can be calibrated in static mode by use of gauge blocks and optical flat. Dynamic behavior of the probe is measured by use of flick or multi wavelength standard.

Use of gauge blocks and optical flat for probe calibration is a method usually recommended by manufactures. Two or more-gauge blocks are wrung on optical flat to create the step-height pattern. Then, optical flat is mounted on rotating table of form measurement device. After leveling is done, rotation of table will cause that probe tip slides over the gauge block of different length, Figure 2. In that way different traceable displacement steps are made to meet measurement ranges. In that way, probe is calibrated only in few positions in static measurement condition and dynamic behavior of the probe cannot be checked.

Fig. 2. Probe calibration with gauges and optical flat. [4]

Another widely used standard for probe calibration is flick standard, Figure 3. Flick standards or magnification standards are widely used to calibrate the sensitivity of form measuring instruments. They are made of a cylinder with a flat part on the circumference and embody a well-defined roundness deviation. The application of flick standards is efficient and functional since they allow us to calibrate the roundness instrument in its normal dynamic operational mode [5].

Fig. 3. Probe calibration with gauges and optical flat. [5]

Probe calibration in dynamic mode also can be done by using multi wavelength standards which is a spatial embodiment of a superposition of several sinusoidal waves, Figure 4. [6] Calibration is done in the same way as with the flick standard. Advantage of calibration of form measuring instrument with multi wavelength standards is that beside the information of form deviation of standard frequency space representation of measured profile is available.

Fig. 4. Probe calibration with multi wavelength standard. [6]

The traceability and dynamic performance of the probes are obtained using various methods developed by NMIs for their own specific devices. There is no standard or calibration guide available describing calibration of reference form measuring devices. The number of papers that describe such a process is very limited and very specific for the modified form measuring devices and probes used as a reference. Calibrations of these modified devices are complex and require specific investigations.

The aim of Probe Trace project is to increase understanding of the current state of the art existing calibration methods FOR form measurement probes and to compare them against novel methods for investigations of measurement probes in static and dynamic measurement conditions. [1]

Within Probe Trace project use of displacement transducers for probe calibration in dynamic and static mode will be investigated. As it was the case with the roughness standards, by applying a displacement generator, it is possible to simulate different types of standards (step-height, flick and multi wavelength standard or any arbitrary geometry) with different nominal values of characteristic parameters. In this application, it is important to emphasize that the spindle is stationary, and the piezoelectric element causes the probe to deflect by displacement, Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Probe calibration with displacement transducer.

Thus, when the probe is calibrated, rotation can be checked afterwards typically by using a hemisphere standard.

IV. NOISE REDUCTION METHODS

Measurement devices for form and roughness uses measurement probe that converts the displacement into an electrical signal. In addition to the form/roughness information, the measurement signal can contain undesirable noise due to mechanical, electrical, thermal and other influences that can lead to an error in the measurement result.

Given the growing demands to reduce measurement uncertainty especially in the form and roughness measurement, noise is a limiting factor.

The presence of a significant level of noise in the measurement result of roundness and roughness will cause repeatable measurement parameters like Ra or $RONt$ (although the noise is random) but with measurement bias. Part of the solution is averaging the measuring profile point-by-point before calculating the parameter, but the time and usefulness to take an average of many measurements is limited, and this does not basically solve the

problem. Novel method that will be investigated in this project is based on Random Noise Bias Removal where only a few repeated measurements are needed to obtain unbiased results [7]. Software toolset based on random noise bias reduction will be created in a way that can be used in any commercial form and surface measurement device that can provide electronic data output to decrease uncertainties in form and roughness measurements.

IV. CONCLUSION

The overall aim of Probe Trace project is to develop traceable and cost-effective measurement capabilities for the calibration of form and surface roughness standards using portable traceable displacement generators as a stand-alone device after its calibration by laser interferometers under static ($\pm 1000 \mu\text{m}$) and dynamic ($\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$) measurement conditions.

That requires research since drifts and unpredicted behaviour of such systems degrade their high precision properties. In Probe Trace project a detailed investigation on how to use the displacement transducers as portable displacement generators will be conducted and by best practice guides on this topic will be prepared.

By realizing the goals of this project NMIs will be able to calibrate their reference stylus instruments using portable displacement generators to achieve traceability with measured uncertainties better than 10 nm. Since calibration using portable displacement generators allows continuous sampling NMIs will be able to better understand error mapping of the reference stylus instruments and expand the measuring range of calibration.

The project will enable direct traceable calibration to the SI unit, the metre of contact measuring probes, in static and dynamic mode using displacement generators with an uncertainty better than 10 nm. Obtained results will be used to prepare best practice guides and will contribute to the establishment of new standards for primary calibration of flick standards or multi wavelength standards.

Noise is one of the main challenges of surface roughness and form measurements. In this project, noise reduction software including the use of numerical methods for random noise bias reduction will be developed in a way that can be used in any commercial form and surface measurement device that can provide electronic data output.

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